

Supplementary material for “Quantification of tumour evolution and heterogeneity via Bayesian epiallele detection”

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June 2, 2017

A Extraction of viable loci

In Figure 1 is an example of an observed locus before any preprocessing steps have been taken. The locus is defined naturally since it does not overlap with any other observed sequencing reads. Note that several sequencing reads only partially overlap and many do not overlap at all. In addition, several CpG measurements are missing from the middle of some reads due to the paired-end sequencing protocol that was used to generate the data (sometimes the paired ends may not span the full length of the DNA fragment).

Intuitively this locus should be split into two loci as the two blocks of reads overlap by a single CpG which is not enough to phase the inferred epialleles. We implemented the following algorithm to split the observed sequencing reads into sensible loci.

1. Specify the minimum number of contiguous CpGs d_{min} and the minimum number of reads N_{min} required in order for a locus to be admissible (we used $d_{min} = 6$ and $N_{min} = 100$ in practice).
2. Specify the maximum proportion of missing data that is allowed (we used 25% in practice).
3. If the observed locus contains more than 25% missing data move to the next step, otherwise skip to step 4.
- 3(a). Represent the observed reads as a matrix with all non-missing measurements equal to 1 and all missing values represented with 0. Use hierarchical clustering to split the reads into two groups using the hamming distance.

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Figure 1: An example of an observed locus (chr1:15,232,224-15,232,587) before preprocessing.

- 3(b). If the two groups contain less than 25% of the missing data then proceed to the next step. Otherwise repeat the clustering above with three groups and so forth.
4. Discard any loci that fail to meet the minimum values of d and N .

We demanded that, in addition to the loci as a whole, each CpG site should not contain more than 25% missing data. Any CpGs that failed to meet this constraint were discarded. This helped to trim low-coverage CpGs from at the edges of observed loci (for example, the very leftmost CpG in Figure 1). The resulting loci after preprocessing are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The two loci that are extracted from the observed data in Figure 1.

B MAP estimate for ϵ

Given \mathbf{X} , \mathbf{w} , Q and uniform priors $p(\mathbf{X}|Q)$ and $p(\mathbf{w}|Q)$ the MAP estimate for the hyperparameter ϵ is given by maximising the log of the posterior (2):

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}(\epsilon) &= \log p(\mathbf{Y}|\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{w}, \epsilon, Q) \\
 &= \log \prod_{i=1}^N \prod_{\mu=1}^d p(y_{i\mu}|x_{w_i\mu}, \epsilon, Q) \\
 &= \alpha_0 \log \epsilon + \alpha_1 \log(1 - \epsilon).
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Note that on the second line that if read \mathbf{y}_i originates from epiallele q then $w_i = q$. Recall that $\alpha_1 = \sum_{i,\mu} \delta_{y_{i\mu}, x_{w_i\mu}}$ and $\alpha_0 = \sum_{i,\mu} 1 - \delta_{y_{i\mu}, x_{w_i\mu}}$ denote the total number of matches and mismatches between the observed reads \mathbf{y} and the corresponding epialleles \mathbf{x} at this particular loci. Solving $d\mathcal{L}/d\epsilon = 0$ yields $\epsilon = \alpha_0/(\alpha_0 + \alpha_1)$.

C Simulation results

Figure 3: Proportion of observed reads attributed to the correct underlying epiallele as a function of N (the number of sequencing reads at the simulated locus). Parameters were fixed to $\epsilon = 0.05$, $d = 6$ and $Q = 3$.

Figure 4: Proportion of observed reads attributed to the correct underlying epiallele as a function of d (the number of CpGs at the simulated locus). Parameters were fixed to $N = 100$, $\epsilon = 0.05$ and $Q = 3$.

Figure 5: Proportion of observed reads attributed to the correct underlying epiallele as a function of ϵ (the noise level). Parameters were fixed to $N = 100$, $d = 6$ and $Q = 3$.

D Purity estimation

Figure 6: Empirical density plots of ξ , the proportion of epialleles at a locus that are different from normal tissue. The distribution of ξ will depend on the tumour purity since samples that are contaminated with less normal tissue will exhibit a greater deviance from the matched normal tissue epialleles. On this basis, the rightmost maxima (marked with a dashed vertical line) of the empirical densities are interpreted as a proxy for sample purity.

E Supplementary figures

Figure 7: Phylogenetic tree generated from exome sequencing data from the same tumour that is studied in the main text. The exome data were generated and analysed independently as part of the Jamal-Hanjani et al., 2017 study. GL denotes germline.

Figure 8: Box plots of the Shannon entropy of the epiallele distribution across the seven tumour regions (R1-R7) after decontamination of normal tissue.

F Comparison to alternative measures of disorder

As discussed in the main text the *epiallele entropy* provides a measure of epigenetic disorder within each tissue sample. In this section we compare our epiallele entropy approach to previously proposed measures of epigenetic disorder. In particular, we will compare the *epipolymorphism score* from Landan et al. (2012), the *methylation entropy* from Xie et al. (2011) and the *proportion of discordant reads* (PDR) approach from Landau et al. (2014).

Both the epipolymorphism score and the PDR score are restricted to loci with 4 CpGs. We have therefore restricted this comparison to only loci with 4 CpGs of which there 38,831 in total across all of our tissue samples. Furthermore, none of the comparators can handle missing data so any reads with a missing CpG measurement were discarded. As described in the main text for our

epiallele entropy approach we used the distribution of epialleles after marginalisation over the \mathbf{w} parameter and any epialleles that had a frequency of less than 5% were discarded.

Box plots comparing the four different measures are shown in Figure 9. All four methods attribute lower disorder scores to the normal tissue. Low purity tumour regions such as R5, R6 and R7 are also given lower disorder scores by all four approaches. The greatest difference between normal and tumour tissue is observed using our epiallele entropy measure. Our method has the additional advantage that it can handle an arbitrary number of CpGs per locus and missing data.

Figure 9: Box plots comparing different epigenetic disorder measures.

G Experimental datasets

The RRBS data are available at the European Nucleotide Archive under accession numbers ERS1546024, ERS1546025 and ERS1546026.

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H TRACERx consortium members

The TRACERx study (Clinicaltrials.gov no: NCT01888601) is sponsored by University College London (UCL/12/0279) and has been approved by an independent Research Ethics Committee (13/LO/1546). TRACER is funded by Cancer Research UK (grant number C11496/A17786) and coordinated through the Cancer Research UK & UCL Cancer Trials Centre.

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